

The Geomorphology of River Meanders in the Nile Channel South of Assiut Barrages, Assiut Governorate.

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Abstract:

This study addresses the geomorphology of river meanders in the Nile channel south of the Assiut Barrages in Assiut Governorate. The introduction outlines the research methodology by defining the problem, which revolves around the factors responsible for changes in the Nile's course. It examines the rates of erosion and deposition at the Al-Muti'a meander, as well as the problems resulting from these geomorphological processes in the study area. The objectives focus on assessing the potential for mitigating the issues arising from erosion and deposition within river meanders. The research investigates the geomorphological phenomena associated with river meanders along the Nile. These include natural factors such as geological and structural characteristics, vertical and lateral erosion processes, and biological and organic influences, as well as human factors such as discharge fluctuations, cultivation on riverbanks, wave action generated by river navigation, dredging operations on the riverbanks, and the construction of stone groynes. Furthermore, the study examines the dynamics of horizontal erosion and deposition, as well as various features associated with river meanders. As a result, the study successfully identifies changes in channel dimensions and explores related features such as lateral bars, levees, scour holes, and backswamps.

Key Words: River Meanders, Assiut Governorate, Geomorphology

Introduction:

The study of the **geomorphology of river meanders** in the Nile channel within the study area aims to understand the factors influencing the movement of riverbanks and the transformations experienced by the river channel. These changes include **geomorphological hazards**, as well as the processes of **erosion, deposition, and lateral migration** of the river course, all of which contribute to the development of geomorphological phenomena related to erosion and sedimentation.

The river continuously strives toward a state of **hydraulic equilibrium and stability** through the dynamic interplay of erosion and deposition. Therefore, this research focuses on the **geomorphological features associated with riverbanks**, examining how they evolve over time and under various influencing factors.

Study Area Definition:

Assiut Governorate is located in Upper Egypt. It is bordered to the north by Minya Governorate, to the south by Sohag Governorate, to the east by the Red Sea Governorate, and to the west by the New Valley Governorate. Astronomically, the governorate extends between **latitude 26°45' and 27°43' N** and **longitude 30°45' and 31°45' E** (Figure 1).

The total area of Assiut Governorate is approximately **25,926 km²**, representing around **2.6% of Egypt's total area**. The **inhabited area** constitutes about **1,562.29 km²**, or nearly **6% of the governorate's total area**.

Assiut's climate is part of the **hyper-arid desert region**, characterized by high temperatures and low precipitation. The average temperature reaches **29.5°C in summer**, while it drops to **14.5°C in winter**. The highest recorded temperature is **48.5°C**, and the lowest is **-2°C**. The **average annual rainfall** is very low, around **0.7 mm**, which, combined with the high temperatures, results in a **high evaporation rate** (Ashraf Abu El-Fotouh & Mohamed El-Shennawy, 2009).

Within the study area, the Nile Valley is divided into four **geomorphological units**:

1. The Nile channel and its associated features.
2. The floodplain.
3. The marginal desert zone (transitional area).
4. The valley sides of the Nile.

The study primarily focuses on the Nile channel south of the Assiut Barrages. The current length of the Nile within this sector is approximately 57 km, representing around 4.6% of the Nile's total length within Egypt. This segment lies between latitude 26°45' and 27°12' N, and features a variety of geomorphological phenomena, including:

- The main river channel and its meanders
- Active secondary channels
- Remnants of abandoned channels
- Old and newly formed river islands, some of which have merged with the sedimentary fabric of the floodplain
- Lateral levees and embankments, among other forms, "Which represents approximately 4.6% of the total length of the Nile River."

Asyut has a population of over 4 million people, with a significant Coptic presence. Muslims and Christians have lived together in Asyut and at times there have been clashes. In July 2013, a large number of Christians took to the streets to protest Muslim extremism in Asyut.^[10]

Whether Christian or Muslim, Asyut is home to a very conservative society and in October, 2016 Upper Egypt's first beauty pageant, which was to be held in Asyut, had to be canceled due to death threats and security issues.^[11]

"Fig (1): Location of Assiut Governorate among the Governorates of the Republic."

Source: Based on data from Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics (CAPMAS), *Assiut Governorate Profile* (Cairo: CAPMAS, 2017), p. 10.

Research Problem and Questions:

Rivers, as one of the most significant agents shaping the Earth's surface, exhibit a clear dynamic nature that fluctuates between erosion and deposition. Previous studies indicate that this dynamic behavior has been considerably altered, especially after the construction of the High Dam, which largely blocked sediment transport downstream. This has potentially led to changes in the river's natural characteristics, including discharge volume and sediment properties, resulting in a variety of geomorphological phenomena. However, the extent of such changes remains unclear, which is what the present study seeks to investigate by answering the following research questions:

- To what extent do geological and hydrological characteristics, on the one hand, and economic activities, on the other, influence the development of river meanders in the Nile channel within the study area?
- Do the mechanical and mineralogical properties of banks and islands affect the evolution of river meanders?
- What are the main factors responsible for the changes in the Nile River's course?
- What are the rates of erosion and deposition at the Al-Muti'a meander, located south of the Assiut Barrages?
- What is the nature of the problems associated with geomorphological phenomena at the meanders of the Nile channel?
- To what extent is it possible to address the issues resulting from erosion and deposition in river meanders?

First: Factors Influencing Riverbank Movement

The problem of bank collapses along the Nile River is a geomorphological phenomenon that predates the construction of the High Dam. It used to occur following seasonal floods, particularly large ones. However, the issue intensified after the dam's construction, which retained approximately 98% of the suspended sediment load.

1. Natural Factors:

A. Geological and Structural Characteristics of the Nile Channel

The geological formations exposed in the study area range in age from the Lower Eocene to the Upper Pliocene, in addition to Pleistocene and Recent deposits. The Eocene formations represent the oldest exposed rock units, covering approximately 77.23% of the total area under study. In contrast, the Pliocene formations cover only 0.86% of the area and are composed of alternating layers of sandstone, gravel, marl clay, conglomerates, and quartz. The thickness of the Pliocene formations in the Assiut area reaches up to 60 meters.

The Pleistocene deposits occupy around 4.3% of the study area and consist of sand, gravel, pebbles, marl clay, silt sand, and quartz-rich silt. The thickness of these deposits reaches approximately 67.5 meters in the Assiut region (Said, 1981, p.116)

B. Vertical and Lateral Erosion Processes

The instability in riverbank elevations is primarily due to the nature of the riverbed and bank sediments. When rocks are less resistant to erosion, they are easily worn away, leading to widening of the river channel and deepening of its bed. Conversely, if the sediments are more resistant, such as coarse sand or gravel, they cannot be easily transported. Over time, the riverbed becomes covered with these coarse materials, increasing its roughness (Abdel Hamid Ahmed Kleyo, 1985, p.38).

Lower erosion rates are observed in beds and banks with relatively coarse textures, as a significant portion of the river's energy is consumed in overcoming the friction caused by this roughness (Mohamed Mahmoud Taha, 1988, p.157).

There is an inverse relationship between channel narrowness and lateral erosion, and a strong connection exists between lateral erosion and river meander zones, where erosional activity intensifies along the concave banks. This causes loosening and displacement of riverbank materials, often resulting in bank collapses and landslides. Vortex currents play a major role in lateral erosion, especially in meander zones, where these currents erode the banks beneath the water surface, weakening their structure until parts collapse into the channel.

C. Biological and Organic Factors

Vegetation contributes to erosion by the growth of radial and tap roots, which widen and multiply rock joints. Likewise, many burrowing animals, such as termites and worms, play a significant role in soil fragmentation due to their large populations (Mohamed Sabry Mahsoub, 2004, p.36).

These organisms contribute actively to bank collapses by digging burrows and tunnels in the riverbank soils. For example, earthworms fragment rocks and transport loosened materials across different areas (Farouk El-San'allah El-Omari, 1999, p.168). In the case of the western bank opposite Al-Muti'a Island, lateral erosion has been attributed to tree root growth, which weakens soil cohesion and is followed by erosion and sediment transport by the flowing water.

In some cases, grass growth on the riverbed and banks helps to stabilize or reduce the movement of fine materials, thus limiting erosion. However, this is offset by the continuous action of water — both from surface river currents and horizontal groundwater flow — which continues to erode and undermine the banks (Mohamed Mahmoud Jaser, 1987, p.45).

2. Human Factors

A. Discharge Fluctuations

River discharge refers to the volume of water present at a given moment, measured in cubic meters per second (m^3/s). There is a direct relationship between discharge, flow velocity, and sediment transport capacity (both quantity and particle size), which in turn affects erosive power. Increased water volume enhances the river's ability to overcome frictional resistance from the bed and banks (Mohamed Sabry Mahsoub, 1997, p.140).

Discharge fluctuations are closely linked to bank collapses, especially when lower discharge levels cause a drop in water level, leaving banks exposed and vulnerable to collapse. Steep bank slopes, combined with high elevation above water level, exacerbate instability. Vortex motion contributes to structural imbalance and eventual collapse (Ibrahim Ali Obeidou, 1982, pp.210–212).

Fakhri Moussa Nakhla (1985) attributed this phenomenon to differences in subsurface water movement. For example, water velocity in coarse sandy soils may reach 2.11 m/day, while in clayey soils, it can be as low as 0.021 m/day. This continuous fluctuation affects bank stability, leading to persistent shifts toward horizontal equilibrium and resulting in ongoing bank collapses.

B. Agriculture on Riverbanks

Riverbanks are indicators of channel dynamics, including narrowing, widening, and lateral migration. After the construction of the High Dam, these geomorphological features lost their traditional significance. Reduced discharge caused the river to retreat from its former banks, leading to the formation of new floodplain margins.

In many areas, the merging of islands with riverbanks led residents to cultivate these newly exposed lands, even using machinery to level and mix nutrient-poor soils with sediments from older banks. This is particularly risky after the loss of silt deposition. The use of heavy agricultural machinery, combined with planting trees (like palms), has led to increased soil pressure and upper bank collapse, especially when repeated irrigation is involved. Additionally, high sand content in these new banks contributes to instability and erosion toward the river and islands.

C. Waves Generated by River Transport

Parts of the channel experience lateral erosion due to waves caused by boats and barges that navigate the Nile for fishing and cargo transport. The effect intensifies where the navigable channel narrows — especially near islands — as wave energy rapidly reaches the riverbanks, causing sub-base erosion, collapse, and damage to protective stone linings (Osama Hussein Shaaban, 2005, p.78).

Field observations confirm constant ferry movement from the western bank to the river islands in the study area, contributing to the instability and erosion of the western bank.

D. Sand and Soil Dredging on Stone Riverbanks

Soil dredging is a major issue leading to complete soil degradation, not just at the dredging site but also in adjacent areas, which are left unsupported and prone to collapse. Human activity, particularly the extraction of soil as raw material for brick-making, strips the soil of its vital components — elements that are hard to replace (Nasr El-Din Mahmoud Ahmed Salem, 2003, p.194).

Dredged lands often lie below the level of surrounding terrain, resulting in poor soil quality due to salt accumulation from irrigation water seepage. Despite legal protection of agricultural lands, the financial gains from soil extraction continue to drive this practice, leading to rapid land degradation.

E. Stone Groynes

Stone groynes are constructed to protect the Nile River channel, particularly at concave meander banks, which are subjected to strong water pressure and rapid current flow. These groynes must be firmly anchored into the concave side of the riverbend to provide structural stability. However, while they help reduce the rate of erosion, they do not eliminate it entirely—their impact is typically temporary (Ahmed Ibrahim Mohamed Saber, 2007, p.311).

To be effective, the stones used must be securely fixed along the river channel's side, extending from the riverbed up to levels higher than the maximum flood stage. The angles formed by the aligned rocks must be intentionally irregular, and the downstream-facing slope should be rough and rugged to resist erosion (Salah El-Din Ali El-Shami, 1995, p.375).

Stone groynes play an important role in protecting the riverbanks, especially along the concave sides of meanders, and behind dams and barrages where erosion is prevalent (Nasr El-Din Mahmoud Ahmed Salem, 2000, p.163). They are also crucial in safeguarding the northern banks of large river islands. However, despite their usefulness, groynes may pose a risk to the downstream riverbanks, as vortex currents often develop behind them, leading to lateral erosion of the banks (Kingham, D., 1998, p.99).

Second: The Dynamics of Horizontal Erosion and Deposition – A Case Study of the Al-Muti'a Meander

Lateral erosion occurs when the main river current shifts toward the concave bank of a meander. This shift generates hydraulic forces that intensify erosion on that side. Simultaneously, reverse flow carries eroded sediments from the concave bank and deposits them along the convex bank (Konsoer et al., 2016, p.86).

The point of inflection in a meander corresponds to the shallowest parts of the river, where depositional bars form. According to sedimentation principles, the river first deposits sediments, creating bars that eventually evolve into sediment islands when they reach the floodplain level. These processes occur continuously but become especially prominent during major floods.

During such high floods, water covers the entire surface of bars and most islands that haven't yet reached floodplain elevation. Because of reduced flow velocity over these features, sediment accumulation increases, enhancing the growth of bars and islands. Even fully formed islands continue to grow during major floods, eventually reaching the natural levee height or slightly exceeding the adjacent floodplain level, similar to the formation of natural levees.

At the Al-Muti'a meander, the highest erosion rates in the study area were recorded:

- Western bank erosion: approximately 4,620.6 meters
- Eastern bank erosion: approximately 8,378 meters
- Eastern bank deposition: approximately 4,702.5 meters
- Western bank deposition: approximately 6,169 meters(See Figure 2)

Fig (2): Erosion and Deposition at the Al-Muti'a Meander in 2020 (Eastern Meander)."

Figure (1) Landslides and sedimentation in Ma'alula Science area, 2020

Third: Geomorphological Features Associated with Nile River Meanders

1. Changes in Channel Dimensions

A. Cross-Sections

A cross-section of a river refers to the topographic profile perpendicular to the river's course, encompassing both the valley sides and the valley floor, including the main river channel. These cross-sections reflect the geomorphological evolution of the river (El-Sayed El-Sayed El-Husseiny, 1988, p.216).

Changes in the hydrological conditions—such as flow velocity, discharge volume, and channel width—impact the shape of the cross-section through varying erosion and deposition processes. The form of the cross-section differs significantly between meandering and straight segments of the river, depending on the characteristics of the surrounding region.

In the study area, the cross-sections vary between straight and meandering shapes. The presence of river islands and sediment bars contributes to these variations, sometimes increasing the width when islands are present, and narrowing when they merge with the riverbanks. Hence, channel width fluctuates depending on the dominant geomorphological processes.

Bank stability depends on several factors, including bank height and slope, soil cohesion and composition, and water levels. Bank failure often results in mass wasting of bank material, occasionally as vertical sliding of entire layers into the river (Mostafa et al., 1977, p.94).

Downstream from dams, cross-sectional morphology is influenced by two main factors:

1. Vertical erosion caused by sediment-free water released from behind the dam, which gradually transforms the channel from a wide, shallow form to a narrow, deep one.
2. Lateral erosion due to bank undercutting. The High Dam has contributed to channel widening at the expense of ongoing bank collapse (Mamdouh Tohamy Abdel-Hay, 1992, p.284).

From the field surveys and 1:5000 hydrotopographic maps, cross-sections were drawn to:

- Identify the widest and narrowest sections.
- Examine how islands affect channel morphology.

The findings were:

- Maximum channel width was recorded at Gezirat Al-Nakhila: 1,487.2 meters, due to the merging of Gezirat Al-‘Auna with the floodplain.
- Minimum width was recorded at Nag‘ Abd Al-Rasoul: 184 meters, due to island merger with the western bank.

- Average depth during low flow: 3.44 m
During flood: 7.84 m
Overall average: 5.64 m, compared to 7.5 m before the High Dam (El-Husseiny, 1991, P.8)
 - Maximum depth: 7.3 m at Maghris
 - Minimum depth: 3.17 m at Beni Feiz
- Asymmetrical bank slopes were observed, especially in meanders like Al-Muti'a and Mashta, with more erosion on concave banks and more deposition on convex banks.
- Irregular bed slopes were caused by islands and sandbars, both lateral and central, raising parts of the channel bed and leading to morphological variation (Brooks, 1994, P.56).

b. Longitudinal Profile

The longitudinal profile of a river refers to the concave curve that represents the river's slope from source to mouth (El-Husseiny, 1988, P.15). This slope determines the flow velocity, enabling a balance between erosion and deposition. Rivers strive to maintain an overall slope that allows for such equilibrium.

Despite variations, most rivers show a concave upward profile, especially in their upper courses (Dury, 1970, p.220). The profile is influenced by underlying rock type and surface gradient (Hassan Abu Samour & Hamed Al-Khatib, 1999, p.36).

Hydrological factors also affect the profile:

- In sediment-poor sections, the river tends to erode and deepen the channel to generate new sediment.
- As sediment load increases, erosive capacity decreases, and channel slope declines, establishing a new dynamic equilibrium (Mohamed Safi El-Din Abu El-Ezz, 1976, P.163).

The construction of dams causes bed erosion, disturbing equilibrium and reducing the longitudinal slope. Yet, erosion often remains parallel to the original riverbed, maintaining its shape (Abdel-Hay, 1992, P.290).

The longitudinal profile reflects:

- Hydrological characteristics, such as discharge and flow velocity
- Channel form, bed roughness, and dominance of either erosion or deposition

A 1982 study by the High Dam Side Effects Institute identified three types of longitudinal **profiles**:

1. Mid-channel profile: Captures the central points of straight segments.
2. Deepest-point profile: Follows the lowest elevation points, representing maximum slope.

3. Average bed elevation profile: Calculated using average depth at known points, representing mean slope.

Findings:

- The profile is irregular, with alternating deep pools and shallow bars, with 1.7 m average elevation difference.
- These variations cause channel instability, increasing meandering.
- Some submerged islands and sandbars have elevations only 1.5 m below the water surface, like at Al-Nakhila (Abutig District), posing risks to navigation.
- The thalweg (deepest path) oscillates across the channel, leaning eastward for 57.26% of its total length (106.5 km), attributed to Froude's Law (Mohamed Awad Mohamed, 1950, p.123).

The High Dam has intensified bed erosion and deepened the riverbed throughout Egypt's section of the Nile.

Lateral Bars

Lateral bars are formed through sediment deposition within the river channel, often taking the form of longitudinal ridges. These may act as nuclei for island formation if complete depositional conditions are met. When deposition occurs along one side of the channel, it results in lateral bars, which represent a mode of lateral floodplain expansion.

Sandy bars are widespread in the riverbed, particularly after the construction of the High Dam, due to flow turbulence. These bars form either under low or high flow velocities, but tend to disappear under moderate flow (Mamdouh Tohamy Abdel-Hay, 1992, p.214). Over time, these bars grow and shift, often merging with the adjacent floodplain, prompting the river to erode one or both banks in an attempt to re-widen its channel (Saber Amin El-Dessouky, 2004, p.184).

Sloughs (Water Arms)

Sloughs are shallow water arms found along both sides of the river in the study area. They are the result of hydrological action, particularly around meanders, or where sediment islands have merged with the floodplain. This merging usually begins on the southern side of the island, which narrows the water channel and accelerates siltation.

The growth of reed vegetation in these areas promotes further sedimentation, gradually raising the land above the river level, preventing water access except during floods.

Scour Holes

Scour holes are deep, vertical natural pits that occur below the main riverbed level. They may appear circular or elongated and often cluster in groups. They are found near meander bends,

bridge piers, revetments, and channel bifurcations. These depressions are typically caused by vortex currents, often resulting from human interventions such as bank protection works, or natural hydrological processes associated with flow division.

Their formation is influenced by water levels, flow velocity, sediment concentration, sediment size, and hydro-morphological variations in the channel.

Back Swamps

Back swamps are shallow depressions that occur at the outer edges of the floodplain, just before it merges with the valley side. They reflect depositional conditions, flood behavior, and variation in water levels from year to year. Though traditionally associated with floodwater scouring, this alone does not fully explain their formation, especially in wide floodplains (Taha Mohamed Gad, 1981, p.24).

These marginal areas receive less sediment than zones adjacent to the river, as only major floods can deposit sediment there. In contrast, areas close to the channel receive regular sedimentation with every flood (Abdel-Hay, 1992, p.218). Back swamps are typically scattered, discontinuous, and non-linear, unlike defined drainage channels.

Back swamps are supplied with water from:

- Direct floodwater inflow during high floods, which remains trapped due to low elevation and fine-textured soils that inhibit infiltration.
- Lateral seepage during moderate and low floods.
- Drainage water discharged by local farmers into these depressions.

Conclusion

The study explores the geomorphological features associated with river meanders of the Nile in the study area through detailed analysis:

1. Longitudinal changes in the riverbed reflect vertical erosion activity and bed irregularities due to alternating pools and bars.
2. The current river course has narrow water widths, caused by intensified vertical incision, leading to lower water levels and reduced width.
3. Human activities—such as cultivation of banks and islands, plowing with modern machinery, and wave action from riverboats—contribute to bank instability.
4. Other anthropogenic effects include vegetation removal, soil dredging, stone groyne construction, and flow manipulation during the winter closure, all contributing to erosion and collapse.

5. Erosion rates on eastern meander banks exceed those on the western side, explained by Ferrel's Law; the reverse is true for western meanders.
6. Field studies revealed numerous geomorphological features along the longitudinal profile, including abandoned channels, sloughs, sandbars, meanders, and islands, indicating significant morphological change.
7. Vertical incision led to shallower water levels and reduced width across most sections.
8. The average depth of the channel is now 5.64 m, compared to 7.84 m before the High Dam.
9. Active vertical erosion and bed irregularities dominate due to pool–bar sequences.
10. Despite the proliferation of lateral bars, they remain dominant depositional features, especially in meander zones.
11. Water cross-section variability is high (CV = 88.9%), reflecting hydrological influence on bank erosion and collapse.
12. The river gradient is 1 meter per 14.5 km, lower than the national average of 1:12 km.
13. The thalweg (deepest line) oscillates laterally and lacks a fixed path.
14. Scour holes are found throughout meander sections—except near Assiut Barrage—and are linked to human interventions.
15. Water surface width decreased by 55% post-High Dam, as islands merged with the floodplain, and abandoned channels emerged.
16. Reiterated: vertical incision dominates and has reshaped the longitudinal riverbed.
17. Bank erosion and deposition lengths were balanced before the dam, but decreased afterward due to stone reinforcements.
18. Pre-dam spatial distribution of erosion/deposition confirmed lateral and longitudinal migration, maintaining channel dimensions.
19. The dam construction phase saw major hydrological shifts: sediment retention and reduced discharge.
20. The modern phase shows a decline in erosion and deposition, attributed to bank protection structures

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